

Underutilization of Smart Pump Safety Features

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Background

- ❖ Approximately 5% of inpatients in the U.S. experience an adverse drug event during their hospital stay (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2017)
- ❖ Safe Medication Administration through Technology (Smart) pumps deliver intravenous medications with fewer errors than regular pumps by using built-in software and programmable drug dictionaries to decrease programming errors by 72% (Makic, 2015; Ohashi, Dalleur, Dykes, & Bates, 2014)
- ❖ 05/2016-04/2017 the RNs in the ICU of an L.A. hospital did not or could not use the smart pump safety features 1,771 times (2.6%)

Implementation Team

- ❖ CNO, ICU Director, Pharmacy Director, 2 Pharmacists, and ICU Educator

Purpose

- ❖ Increase adherence with the use of the safety features of the Sigma Spectrum Infusion System in an ICU
- ❖ Specific Aims
 - ❖ Identify nurses' perceptions of the barriers to adherence
 - ❖ Develop and implement strategies targeting the identified barriers
 - ❖ Evaluate the efficacy of the implemented strategies

Supporting Framework

Methods

- ❖ Study Design: Quality improvement project using pre- and post-implementation data to examine the effects of the implemented interventions on percent adherence
- ❖ Samples: First sample was the IV medication orders two months before the intervention and two months after the intervention. Second sample was the 41 ICU nurses who completed the survey
- ❖ Procedure:
 - ❖ DEFINE: Process maps developed to show steps for adding drugs to drug dictionary and to program the pump
 - ❖ MEASURE: % adherence to using the drug dictionary in the pump was determined. The shift the pump was set was also measured. Web-based survey designed specifically for this project was used by the ICU nursing staff to record their perceived barriers to adherence
 - ❖ ANALYZE: % adherence was easily determined by dividing the number of times a nurse used the drug dictionary by the total number of times the pumps were set. The data from the survey was analyzed to determine which barriers to adherence were most prevalent
 - ❖ IMPROVE: Based on the results from the ANALYZE phase, an improvement plan was developed including entering the drug dictionary information timely, establishing a process to notify pharmacy when a drug is not in the dictionary, educating the nurses (including registry nursing), and including data in ICU performance improvement metrics
 - ❖ CONTROL: Post-implementation data collected, analyzed, and communicated

Results

- ❖ Barriers to Adherence (41 ICU nurses with 59 responses)
 - ❖ Drug not in dictionary (51%)
 - ❖ Lack of knowledge (17%)
 - ❖ Incorrect drug concentration (15%)
 - ❖ Takes too much time (7%)
 - ❖ Dose limits incorrect (5%)
 - ❖ Other (Do Not Know; No STAT Doses) (3%)
 - ❖ Patient safety not impacted (2%)
- ❖ Adherence
 - ❖ Overall: Pre 98.0% Post 98.7% ($p=0.002$)
 - ❖ Day Shift: Pre 98.3% Post 98.4% (*no statistically significant change*)
 - ❖ Night Shift: Pre 97.8% Post 99.1% ($p<0.05$)

Discussion

- ❖ The purpose and the specific aims of the project were met
- ❖ The implemented improvements were supported by research
 - ❖ entering the drug dictionary information timely (Mansfield & Jarrett, 2015)
 - ❖ establishing a process to notify pharmacy when a drug is not in the dictionary (Harding, 2011)
 - ❖ educating the nurses (Pinkney, Trbovich, Fan, Rothwell, Cafazzo, & Easty, 2010)
 - ❖ including data in ICU performance improvement metrics (Gavriloff, 2012)
- ❖ Limitations included the short time improvements were measured, using only one type of pump, and limiting project to one unit in one hospital

Implications

- ❖ Clinical: Improvements made in the ICU will be implemented in the other areas of the hospital to improve patient safety
- ❖ Education: All nurses, including registry personnel, need to be trained on smart pumps and provided updates
- ❖ Research: Adherence by pump brand could be studied
- ❖ Technology: Improvements could include requiring override reason to be entered

